

Synthesis of Some Alkoxy Thiocyanates of Titanium(IV)

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Reactions of $Ti(OR)_4$ (R=ethyl or isopropyl) with acetyl isothiocyanate give products of the type $Ti(OR)_{4-n}(NCS)_n \cdot X$ (when R=Et; n=1 to 3, X=0; n=4, X= CH_3COOEt , when R=Prⁱ; n=1 or 2, X=0). IR spectra and molecular weights of these compounds have also been studied.

TITANIUM alkoxy thiocyanate derivatives have been synthesized for the first time by the reactions of titanium alkoxydes with acetyl thiocyanate in different molar ratio. The products have been characterized on the basis of their elemental analyses, molecular weights and infrared spectra.

Experimental

Rigorous precautions were taken to exclude moisture throughout these investigations.

Titanium alkoxydes¹ and acetyl isothiocyanate² were prepared by the literature methods. Molecular weights were determined in a semi-micro ebulliometer (Gallenkamp) in refluxing benzene and acetone.

IR spectra were recorded in the range 4000-400 cm^{-1} on Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer using KBr plates.

Titanium was estimated as titanium dioxide. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl method.

Reaction of $Ti(OEt)_4$ with CH_3CONCS (1 : 1 molar ratio) :

A mixture of titanium(IV) ethoxide (3.17 g; 0.0013 g mole) and acetyl isothiocyanate (1.38 g; 0.0013 g mole) in cyclohexane (~50 ml) was refluxed for 2 hr and the ester produced was continuously fractionated off azeotropically. Excess of solvent was removed under reduced pressure, when a light yellow solid product was obtained. The product was dried at 30°/0.1 mm of Hg for 3 hr, yield, 3.20 g (Calcd. yield 3.28 g), (Found : Ti, 19.92 ; N, 5.79. Calcd. for $Ti(OEt)_3(NCS)$; Ti, 19.91 ; N, 5.80%).

The products obtained by the reaction of titanium(IV) alkoxydes with acetyl isothiocyanate in different molar ratios are listed in the Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The present communication reports the synthesis of thiocyanato derivatives of Ti(IV) alkoxydes by the reactions of their metal alkoxydes with acetyl isothiocyanate.

TABLE 1—SOME ISOTHIOCYANATES OF TITANIUM(IV) ALKOXYDES

Sl. No.	Reactants (g)	Molar ratio	Yield g (Calcd.)	Product (Nature)	Analysis : Found/(Calcd.)		
					Ti%	N%	Molecular weight
1.	$Ti(OEt)_4 + CH_3CONCS$ (3.11) (1.38)	1 : 1	3.20 (3.28)	$Ti(OEt)_3(NCS)$ (Yellow solid)	19.92 (19.88)	5.79 (5.80)	495* 350** (241)
2.	$Ti(OEt)_4 + CH_3CONCS$ (3.59) (3.21)	1 : 2	3.90 (3.99)	$Ti(OEt)_2(NCS)_2$ (Dark red solid)	18.65 (18.86)	10.97 (11.02)	515* 243** (254)
3.	$Ti(OEt)_4 + CH_3CONCS$ (4.15) (5.51)	1 : 3	4.80 (4.86)	$Ti(OEt)(NCS)_3$ (Dark red solid)	18.02 (17.94)	15.62 (15.73)	271** (267)
4.	$Ti(OEt)_4 + CH_3CONCS$ (3.39) (6.00)	1 : 4	4.28 (4.35)	$Ti(NCS)_4 \cdot X$ (Dark red solid)	13.06 (13.01)	15.34 (15.22)	352** (368)
5.	$Ti(OPr^i)_4 + CH_3CONCS$ (3.94) (1.45)	1 : 1	4.15 (3.94)	$Ti(OPr^i)_3(NCS)$ (Yellow viscous liquid)	17.37 (16.93)	5.07 (4.94)	300** (288)
6.	$Ti(OPr^i)_4 + CH_3CONCS$ (2.15) (1.53)	1 : 2	2.02 (2.12)	$Ti(OPr^i)_2(NCS)_2$ (Yellow crystalline solid)	17.12 (16.99)	10.02 (9.93)	268** (282)

X = CH_3COOEt .

* = Molecular weights in refluxing benzene ; ** = Molecular weights in refluxing acetone.

TABLE 2—CHARACTERISTIC INFRARED ABSORPTION FREQUENCIES OF SOME ALKOXY THIOCYANATES OF TITANIUM

Sl. No.	Compound	νCN	νCS	δNCS	$2\delta\text{NCS}$	$\nu\text{C}-\text{O}$ (Alkoxy)	$\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ (Carbonyl)	$\nu\text{M}-\text{O}$
1.	$\text{Ti}(\text{OEt})_3(\text{NCS})$	2050 s 2010 s	875 s 840 s	—	930 s	1065 s 1015 s	—	605 s 535 s
2.	$\text{Ti}(\text{OEt})_2(\text{NCS})_2$	2020 s	880 m	—	935 w	1065 m 1015 m	—	610 s 550 s(b)
3.	$\text{Ti}(\text{OEt})(\text{NCS})_3$	2170 m 2000 s(b)	880 w	—	—	1015 w	—	610 s 550 (b)
4.	$\text{Ti}(\text{NCS})_4 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{COOEt}$	2150 s 2070 s	865 m(b) 820 m	490 m	945 m	1010 s	1720 s	610 m(b)
5.	$\text{Ti}(\text{OPr}^t)_2\text{NCS}$	2055-2000 s	860 s 815 s	485 s 465 s	925 s	1030-975 s	—	530 s
6.	$\text{Ti}(\text{OPr}^t)_3(\text{NCS})_2$	2170 m	860 s 815 s	—	925 s	1025-990 s	—	625-600 s

s=strong ; m=medium ; w=weak ; b=broad; scanned in nujol (otherwise neat).

The reactions of $\text{Ti}(\text{OEt})_4$ with CH_3CONCS in cyclohexane in different molar ratios are found to be exothermic in nature and can be represented as follows :

While reactions of $\text{Ti}(\text{OPr}^t)_4$ with CH_3CONCS proceed smoothly upto 1 : 2 molar ratios :

Reactions between $\text{Ti}(\text{OPr}^t)_4$ and CH_3CONCS in the 1 : 3 and 1 : 4 molar ratios resulted in the formation of oxy-thiocyanato derivatives of the approximate compositions $\text{TiO}_{0.7}(\text{NCS})_{2.6} \cdot 0.7\text{Y}$ and $\text{TiO}_{0.64}(\text{NCS})_{2.7} \cdot \text{Y}$, respectively. (Y = $\text{CH}_3\text{COOPr}^t$).

Molecular weights of $\text{Ti}(\text{OEt})_3(\text{NCS})$ and $\text{Ti}(\text{OEt})_2(\text{NCS})_2$ compounds could be determined ebullioscopically in refluxing benzene and the compounds were found to be dimeric in nature. In refluxing acetone, both the compounds as well as all other synthesized thiocyanato derivatives of titanium(IV) alkoxides were found to be monomeric. The ethoxy bridged formation may be inferred in the dimeric structures of $\text{Ti}(\text{OEt})_3(\text{NCS})$ and $\text{Ti}(\text{OEt})_2(\text{NCS})_2$ by ir spectra. The dimeric structures of these compounds may be depicted as (a) and (b), respectively :

IR spectra :

The compounds $\text{Ti}(\text{OEt})_3(\text{NCS})$ and $\text{Ti}(\text{OEt})_2(\text{NCS})_2$ have shown strong absorption bands at 2050, 2010 cm^{-1} and 2020 cm^{-1} , respectively in the νCN stretching regions. These νCN band positions are indicative of the presence of N-bonded thiocyanate groups in these compounds³⁻⁵. The νCS stretching frequencies of these derivatives have been observed at about $850 \pm 30 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is again indicative of N-bonded nature of thiocyanate groups in both $\text{Ti}(\text{OEt})_3(\text{NCS})$ and $\text{Ti}(\text{OEt})_2(\text{NCS})_2$ derivatives³⁻⁶. The dimeric nature in these derivatives may be inferred through ethoxide bridging because there is no band observed in the region $2150 \pm 20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is indicative of thiocyanate bridging⁷⁻⁹.

Other thiocyanato derivatives of titanium(IV) alkoxides show bands at $\sim 2150 \pm 20$ and $2020 \pm 20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the νCN stretching regions and bands at about $840 \pm 30 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the νCS stretching regions. These band positions show the presence of bridging thiocyanate groups as well as N-bonded terminal thiocyanate groups in these derivatives. The characteristic frequencies of all these synthesized derivatives have been given in Table 2.

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